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Influence of Neuroticism Personality on the Choice of Conflict Resolution Strategies Among Farmers and Herders Living in Conflict Areas of Adamawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of the neuroticism personality trait on the choice of conflict resolution strategies among farmers and herders living in conflict areas of Adamawa State, Nigeria. A correlational research design was employed for the study. The total participants of the study are 350 registered farmers and herders living in conflict areas were selected using a purposive sampling technique, of which 143 were found to have neuroticism among other personality types. Two instruments were used for the data collection: Eysenck Personality Inventory (EPI) to assess the neuroticism personality, while Thomas-Kilmann's Conflict Mode Instrument (TKI) was used to measure conflict resolution strategies. The instruments were translated into local Languages, Hausa and Fulfulde, respectively. The instruments were validated by experts, checked with Cronbach's alpha and found reliable for use. The Stepwise Method of Multiple Regression was employed to analyze the data. The result shows that, neurotic individuals are found to have a choice for compromising, avoiding and competing conflict resolution strategies ($r = .062, .084$ and $p = .000, .003, \text{ and } .039$). The findings recommend that personality factors should be considered whenever the issue of conflict resolution arises in settling disputes, especially among farmers and herders.

Keywords: Personality, Neuroticism, Conflict, Conflict Resolution.

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Influence of Neuroticism Personality on the Choice of Conflict Resolution Strategies Among Farmers and Herders Living in Conflict Areas of Adamawa State, Nigeria.**Introduction**

Conflict is derived from the Latin word “*conflictus*”, which means to strike together. Conflict is a natural and inevitable fact of human existence (Rahim et al., 2015). Thus, it is part and parcel of the social nature of humankind. It is a form of intense interpersonal, intrapersonal and/or group dissonance between two or more interdependent parties based on incompatible goals, needs, desires, values or attitudes. It is an interactive process manifested in incompatibility and disagreement within or between social entities. Conflict can occur in any aspect of human interaction (Acland, 1990). However, it could be generally agreed that conflict occurs when there is a disagreement between individuals within a group or between two parties. Nahavandi, Denhardt, Denhardt, and Aristigueta (2015) defined conflict as a process in which people have divergent opinions over important issues that affect them, thereby leading to serious disagreement. Conflict is the struggle between two or more actors to attain limited scarce resources or incompatible goals, and each tries to prevent the opponent from attaining the goals.

Conflict resolution is a variety of strategies aimed at terminating conflicts through the constructive solving of problems (Miller, 2003). The evolving movement towards conflict resolution grew out of the belief that there are better options than using violence or going to court, and describes informal methods used by disputants to resolve disputes (Acland, 1990). Conflict Resolution Strategies involve a wide range of measures, processes, and methods of addressing and putting an end to a conflict. The strategies that individuals may employ in situations where their concerns or needs are incompatible

(Nahavandi, et’ tal, 2015). According to Thomas (1976; 2002) conflict resolution approach is a “general and consistent orientation toward the other party and the conflict issues, manifest in observable behaviours that form a pattern and share common characteristics over time” (Kuhn & Poole, 2000).

This study therefore adopted Thomas and Kilmann’s Conflict Resolution Strategies, which include collaborating, competing, avoiding, accommodating and compromising. (Thomas, 1992) identifies these five conflict resolution strategies that individuals may use depending on their personality dispositions toward pro-self or pro-social goals.

1. Avoiding Conflict Strategy: This approach is characterized by inaction and passivity. The avoidance conflict approach is typically used when an individual has reduced concern for their own outcomes as well as the outcomes of others, and also when an individual steps aside and buys time and follows diplomatic methods. During conflict, these avoiders adopt a “wait and see” attitude, often allowing conflict to phase out on its own without any personal involvement. Unfortunately, by neglecting to address high-conflict situations, avoiders risk allowing problems to fester out of control.

2. Accommodating Conflict Strategy: The accommodating conflict resolution strategies are characterized by a great concern for others while having a low concern for one’s own self. This passive pro-social approach emerges when individuals derive personal satisfaction from meeting the needs of others and have a general concern for maintaining stable, positive social relationships. When faced with conflict, individuals with a yielding conflict approach tend to give in to others’ demands

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out of respect for the social relationship to maintain group unity.

3. Competing Conflict Strategy: This strategy maximizes individual assertiveness (concern for self) and minimizes empathy (concern for others). Groups consisting of competitive members generally enjoy seeking domination over others, and typically see conflict as a “win or lose” predicament. Fighters tend to force others to accept their personal views by employing competitive, power tactics (such as arguing, insulting, accusing, and violence) that foster feelings of intimidation.

4. Collaborating Conflict Strategy: This is characterized by an active concern for both pro-social and pro-self behaviour; the cooperation conflict approach is typically used when an individual has elevated interests in their own outcomes as well as in the outcomes of others. During conflict, co-operators collaborate with others in an effort to find an amicable solution that satisfies all parties involved in the conflict. Individuals with this type of conflict approach tend to be highly assertive and highly empathetic at the same time. By seeing conflict as a creative opportunity, collaborators willingly invest time and resources into finding a “win-win” solution.

5. Compromising Conflict Strategy: This approach is typical of individuals who possess an intermediate level of concern for both personal and others’ outcomes. Compromisers value fairness and, in doing so, anticipate mutual give-and-take interactions. By accepting some demands put forth by others, compromisers believe this agreeableness will encourage others to meet halfway, thus promoting conflict resolution.

In application to this study, the goal or aim of every farmer during planting season is to have a bountiful harvest, then sell the farm produce and make profits. On the other hand, the herdsman would always want to have well-fed

and healthy cattle and be able to make profits as well. When any of these expectations was not realizable, either by the herd (cattle) eating up and destroying the farmers’ crops or by the farmer encroaching on grazing reserves or using water reserved for cattle to irrigate their farms, aggression would be triggered. Either of the parties that felt frustrated in achieving their economic goals may decide to resort to showing their displeasure, and as a result, conflict will occur.

The term “personality” in Psychology is a vast term. It is a combination of characteristics and qualities which give an individual a well-defined identity. These characteristics vary from person to person. Personality refers to unique patterns of thinking, feeling, and behaviour of an individual. It involves the person’s habits, traits, physique and other characteristics that he or she possesses. Oxford Dictionary of Psychology defined personality as “the total of the behavioural and mental characteristics that are distinctive of an individual (Colman, 2003). The American Psychological Association (APA, 2019) defined the term personality as “the enduring configuration of characteristics and behaviour that comprises an individual’s unique adjustment to life, including major traits, interests, drives, values, self-concept, abilities, and emotional patterns”. Personality is generally viewed as a complex, dynamic integration or totality shaped by many forces, including hereditary and constitutional tendencies; physical maturation; early training; identification with significant individuals and groups; culturally conditioned values and roles; and critical experiences and relationships. Various theories explain the structure and development of personality in different ways, but all agree that personality helps determine behaviour (APA, 2019). The psychologist Hans Eysenck defines personality as “The more or less stable and enduring organization of a person’s character,

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temperament, intellect and physique which determines his unique adjustment to the environment” (Eysenck 1971 as cited in Mangal (2015). These definitions confirm the fact that Personality is a quite complex concept. It includes everything about a person. Thus, it can't be just a collection of traits but a unique and dynamic structure.

Neuroticism as a personality trait refers to the personality dispositions of an individual who may express stable or unstable emotional manifestations, which include anger, aggression, anxiety, sadness, irritability, insecurity, depression, mood and nervous tension. According to Mathew and Deary (1998), people scoring low on this subscale do not often experience harmful emotions, such as nervousness, moodiness, irritability, or depression. Those who score are mainly susceptible to stress and are quick to react emotionally (Livesley, 2001). (The stable neurotic individuals will be generally less reactive to stressful situations, remaining calm and relaxed and report a low level of negative emotional manifestations; while the unstable are more vulnerable to overreacting to stimuli and find it difficult to calm down once upset (Mathew & Deary, 1998). Neuroticism is a personality type characterized by sadness, moodiness, and emotional instability (McCrae & Costa, 1986). Individuals who are high in this trait tend to experience mood swings, anxiety, irritability, and sadness. Those low in this trait tend to be more stable and emotionally resilient (Marsh, Nagengast & Morin, 2013). Neuroticism has an inherent negative connotation. Mathew and Deary (1998) maintained that it has an enduring tendency to experience negative emotional states and such feelings as anxiety, anger, guilt and depressed mood. Bolger (1990), McCrae and Costa (1986) are of the view that individuals who are high in neuroticism may show more emotional reactions whenever confronted with stressful situations.

Moreover, they seem to use avoiding and distracting coping strategies, such as denying, wishing, thinking and self-criticism, rather than more approachable strategies.

Neuroticism/Stability - A person's level of neuroticism is determined by the reactivity of their sympathetic nervous system. A stable person's nervous system will generally be less reactive to stressful situations, remaining calm and level-headed. Murkherjee (2002) maintained that the neuroticism stability dimension is concerned with the levels of moodiness, irritability, anxiety and discontentedness of an individual as opposed to his stability, calmness, reliability and even temperedness of dispositions. He noted that complex tasks can be well performed with a lower level of anxiety, while simpler tasks are more easily performed by individuals of comparatively high anxiety. Complex levels of problem solving can be better performed by individuals manifesting lower rather than higher levels of anxiety.

Neuroticism/Instability- Someone high in neuroticism, on the other hand, will be much more unstable and prone to overreacting to stimuli and may be quick to worry, anger or fear. They are overly emotional and find it difficult to calm down once upset. High neuroticism is characterized by the tendency to experience unpleasant emotions, such as anger, anxiety, depression, or vulnerability. According to Marsh, Nagengast, and Morin (2013), people with a high neuroticism score tend to experience higher levels of stress and anxiety. They worry about relatively insignificant issues, exaggerate their meaning, and feel unable to cope with stressors. Eysenck (1971) hypothesized that some people have a more responsive sympathetic nervous system than others. Some people remain very calm during emergencies; some people feel considerable fear or other emotions; and some are terrified by even very

minor incidents. According to Eysenck (1971), Eysenck characterizes neuroticism by perfectionism and dissatisfaction. On the other hand, a person with a low neuroticism score will generally experience greater emotional stability. The people who, for the most part, feel more capable of coping with stressful events and setting goals that are suited to their abilities. People with a low neuroticism score tend to be more tolerant of others' failures and remain calmer in demanding situations. People with a high score in neuroticism tend to experience emotional instability and are characterized as angry, impulsive, and hostile. In contrast, people who score low in neuroticism tend to be calm and even-tempered. Eysenck (1971) stated that:

Instable Neuroticism

- i. Gets upset easily
- ii. Experiences a lot of stress and struggles to bounce back after stressful events.
- iii. Worries about many different things
- iv. Experiences dramatic shifts in mood
- v. Feels anxious

Stable Neuroticism

- i. Emotionally stable
- ii. Deals well with stress
- iii. Rarely feels sad or depressed
- iv. Doesn't worry much
- v. Very relaxed.

Adamawa state confronts challenges related to violent conflict between farmers and herders. The fertile soil and climate in the state offer a favourable environment for farmers and herders to thrive, attracting migratory herders from neighbouring states. The farming and herding communities in the state have, for decades, benefited from mutually beneficial relationships- farmers benefit from cattle manure and herders crop residue. This symbiotic practice tied the well-being of the farmers to the well-being of the herder and allowed for most disputes between the two

groups to be resolved amicably, through traditional mediation mechanisms (Kwaja & Ademola, 2017). Abbass (2012) stated that, over the last decades, this interdependence has increasingly deteriorated due to the changing demography, environmental degradation, and climate change, resulting in shrinking natural resources, competition for resources and manipulation of the socio-political diversity of communities. Hence, the transformation of the relationships between the crop cultivators and pastoral herders spontaneously changed from one of complementarity and trust to hostility, violence and wars.

The weakening of community-based dispute resolution mechanisms, rising criminality associated with cattle rustling and raiding of villages, as well as ineffective law enforcement, continue to drive the conflict with wide-ranging implications for the livelihoods of the communities, schools, food security and overall security in the state (Search for Common Ground, 2018). The existence of unbalanced reportage by the media, research articles and interested parties on the farmers and herders' violent conflicts is another predicament of the problem. This awful situation becomes worse, especially when either the farmer or the pastoralist is categorized into a group relating to religion, tribe or region, leading to constant conflict among the agrarian societies. Violent clashes between farmers and herders are largely viewed as attacks perpetrated by male aggressors, while women, children and old people are categorized as vulnerable groups who are caught up in an aggressive web of violence. Many sources revealed that the major sources of conflicts between farmers-herdsmen are land-related issues, especially over grazing fields, which account for the highest percentage of the conflicts in the State.

The neurotic nature of individuals may play a vital role in understanding and the choice of

conflict resolution approach. Having to understand a person's personality is one of the solutions in understanding how to manage or resolve conflict, which will facilitate individuals in improving and achieving the positive outcome in conflict situations (Ahmed et'al, 2010). For over a decade now, Adamawa has been suffering from internal social violence conflict between farmers and herdsmen. This social conflict between these two agrarian groups, who were hitherto good friends and mutual neighbours, claimed the lives of many people, including innocent children, women and old people; farms and farm produce were destroyed, villages were burnt down to ashes, and animals equally killed. Consequently, this conflict affects the livelihoods of the communities, food security and overall security in the state and the education of children, leading to obstacles in their development and mass displacement due to the poor security situation in the conflict areas. Fear of attacks has stopped children from attending schools; these activities have led to the closure of primary, secondary schools and other educational programmes.

The need for conflict resolution in our society is crucial. Efforts to curb farmer-herder violent conflict situations have often been unsuccessful, occasioned not only by the complex nature of humanity but also by the methods and strategies employed. Many studies observed that judicial commissions set up to resolve conflicts between farmers/herders do not yield any effective action. On the whole, the most hated approach of conflict resolution is the police/court, and it is rarely used. It is assumed that conflicting parties in natural settings typically have strategic options, which are believed that there are better than using violence or going to court, and describe informal methods used by disputants to resolve conflicts.

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the neuroticism personality trait and the choice of conflict resolution strategies among

farmers and herders living in conflict areas of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The methodology employed in investigating the influence of the neuroticism personality trait on preference for conflict resolution strategies among farmers and herders living in conflict areas of Adamawa state, Nigeria. The researcher adopted a correlational design for this study. Correlational research is appropriate for comparing and determining whether there are relationships between two or more quantifiable variables and to what degree these relationships exist in the same population or between the same variables in two populations (Leedy & Ormrod, 2010). The design is chosen because the study seeks to establish the relationship between two variables: the neuroticism personality traits and the choice of conflict resolution strategies. The population of the study comprise all the Farmers and Herders living in conflict areas of Numan, Demsa, Lamorde, Song and Girei local governments of Adamawa State. The researcher used 350 total participants who were selected using simple random sampling, from which 143 Neurotic individuals were purposively identified and selected among other personality characteristics. Two instruments were used for data collection. The Eysenck Personality Inventory (EPI) was used to measure participants' personality characteristics (Eysenck, 1971). The TKI Thomas & Kilmann's MODE Instrument (Thomas & Kilmann, 1974) for Conflict Resolution was used to assess participants' conflict resolution approach. The instruments were also translated into Hausa and Fulfulde languages, respectively. The researcher or his assistant independently contacted the respondents. Descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used to analyze the data collected, and results were presented through frequency counts, percentages, and tables.

Multiple regression analysis using a stepwise method was used to test the null hypothesis.

represents 63% were farmers, while a total of 53 participants, representing 37% were herders.

Results

The following tables present the descriptive analysis of the occupation of the participants.

Hypothesis Testing

The following table shows the multiple regression analysis by the stepwise regression method in testing the hypothesis.

Table 1: Distribution of Neuroticism Personality Trait of Participants

S/N	Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
1	Farmers	90	63
2	Herders	53	37
Total		143	100

There is no significant relationship between the neuroticism personality trait and the choice of conflict resolution strategies among farmers and herders living in conflict areas of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Table 1 above shows the frequency and percentage of the neuroticism personality among farmers and herders who participated in the study. A total of 90 participants, which

Table 2: Summary Model of Neuroticism and Conflict Resolution Strategies

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted r Square	Std. Error of Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F. Change	DF 1	DF 2	Sig. F Change
1. Compromising Approach	.254 ^a	.065	.062	3.94854	.065	24.017	1	347	.000
2. Avoiding Approach	.298 ^b	.089	.084	3.90261	.124	9.216	1	346	.003
3. Competing Approach	.317 ^c	.100	.092	3.88412	.011	4.303	1	345	.039

Table 2 above shows the summary model for neuroticism individuals' most chosen strategies of conflict resolution in hierarchical order among the significant variables. The compromising approach of conflict resolution in summary model 1 for neuroticism and conflict resolution explained 6% of the total variance and was therefore significant at F = 24.01 and P = .000. In model 2, the avoiding conflict resolution approach was added, and was significant at F = 16.90, and P = 0.003. The model, therefore, explained 8% of the total variance. For model 3, which is the

competing conflict resolution approach, it was added, and F = 12.80, and P = 0.039 were revealed. The model explained 9% of the total variance among neurotics altogether, indicating 23% of the total variance from the foregoing analysis in their usage of the conflict resolution approach among farmers and herders. The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant of neuroticism personality in the choice of conflict resolution strategies among farmers and herders living in conflict areas in Adamawa State of Nigeria, is therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of this study reveals that neuroticism is significantly related to compromising, avoiding, and competing conflict resolution strategies, and this implies that neurotic farmers/herders do not prefer the collaborating and accommodating strategies for conflict resolution. The finding is also similar to the early findings reported by Igbo, Awopetu and Ekoja (2015), who conducted a study on neuroticism personality dimension and the choice of conflict management strategies. They used the multiple regression analysis whose results showed a significant interactive relationship between neuroticism personality traits and competing conflict resolution strategies of spouses. Similarly, the research of Turkmen, Fatih and Tuna, Muharem (2015) study to find the relationship between the personal traits of the managers and the conflict management methods that they use. Within this context, a survey was conducted on a group of travel agencies and three, four and five-star hotels operating in the seven regions of Turkey. The results concluded that the managers with neurotic traits were revengeful and their personality trait employed the competing method of conflict resolution. However, other findings were in disagreement with the present research reports, such as the study results of Tehrani and Yamini (2019); Basin, Celtin and Tabak (2016) research conducted to determine the personality characteristics that influenced conflict resolution strategies, the results show that there was no existing relationship between neuroticism characteristics and conflict resolution strategies. This disagreement would be due to the nature of conflict, environmental factors, resource issues and the nature of participants.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, Neuroticism influence the choice of preferred conflict resolution strategies among the

farmers and herdsmen in Adamawa State because Neuroticism goes well with the compromising, avoiding and competing approaches in conflict resolution among farmers and herders in Adamawa State.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this research, it is recommended that the personality trait of an individual be considered in issues concerning conflict resolution and strategic options with a view to assisting disputants in adopting helpful resolution strategies.

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